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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **Grape**, **OL**ive and **Durum** wheat food systems

REPORT ON THE STATUS OF THE MED-GOLD COMMUNITY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the initial actions undertaken towards establishing the MED-GOLD community. The categories of stakeholders per sector within the MED-GOLD community are briefly described. Planned activities for engaging and further developing the MED-GOLD community during the course of the project (herein referred to as MED-GOLD) are also described.

With this deliverable, MED-GOLD has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olives, grapes, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olives, grapes, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

This report describes the initial actions undertaken towards establishing the MED-GOLD community, as well as the ones planned for developing and engaging this community. In this context, the MED-GOLD community includes suppliers and end-users within the three agricultural sectors of interest to MED-GOLD – grapes/wine, olives/olive oil and durum wheat/pasta sectors. This community will help us refine and improve the findings from the pilot services as well as validate and upscale those outputs beyond the services developed in MED-GOLD.

MED-GOLD benefits from the involvement of industrial partners identified as world leading organisations in the production of wine, olive oil and pasta (SOGRAPE, DCOOP, and Barilla, respectively). These organisations will play a key role in the co-design and co-development of the pilot climate services (work packages 2, 3 and 4 of MED-GOLD).

For the development of the MED-GOLD community, we started by focusing on the organisations connected to the industrial partners across Europe. Additional organisations were identified from reviewing publications of similar European projects as well as through an online search of relevant organisations operating across Europe in these sectors or related to the agriculture sector more generally. The MED-GOLD community is expected to expand and evolve for the duration of MED-GOLD.

1.1. PURPOSE

This report constitutes deliverable 5.1 “Report on the status of the MED-GOLD Community”. The MED-GOLD community is under development and consists of both public and private European and national organisations involved in different aspects of the three agricultural sectors targeted under MED-GOLD: olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta.

1.2. SCOPE

The type of organisations and their representativeness within MED-GOLD community will be briefly described. Planned activities for engaging and developing MED-GOLD community are also described.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate services	Timely production and delivery (translation and transfer) in customized products (projections, forecasts, information, trends, economic analysis, assessments, etc.) of useful climate-related data, information and knowledge that support adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk management to decision makers
MED-GOLD community	Organisations operating in Europe in the agriculture sector and invited to take part in MED-GOLD through a variety of activities in order to be informed of the development of MED-GOLD as well as help us refine and improve the findings from the pilot services focusing on olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat, and validate and upscale those outputs beyond the services developed in MED-GOLD.
End-user	Organization or person who currently uses or is intended to ultimately use a product or service
Clustering	Joint activities with other climate service related European Commission funded projects via H2020 or other complementary programmes

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ARIMNet	Coordination of Agricultural Research In The Mediterranean Network
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
EU	European Union
EU-MACS	European Market for Climate Services project
MED-GOLD	Referring to the project entitled “Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MED iterranean G rape, O Live and D urum wheat food systems”
RD	Reference documents
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	"A European research and innovation Roadmap for Climate Services" (report of Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of European Commission)	-	-	2015
[RD.2]	"Climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction in Europe" (European Environment Agency report no. 15/2017)	-	-	2017
[RD.3]	"EU Agricultural Outlook For The Agricultural Markets And Income 2017-2030" (European Commission report)	-	-	2017
[RD.4]	"Analysis of existing data infrastructure for climate services" (EU-MACS D 1.3. report)	-	-	2017
[RD.5]	ARIMNet2 Integrated Strategic Research Agenda	-	-	2016
[RD.6]	Communication, dissemination and exploitation management plan	D 7.1.	1.4.	31/05/2018
[RD.7]	Med-Gold final project proposal	-	-	16/10/2017
[RD.8]	MED-GOLD Community Developed	MS 2	1.0	31/05/2018

3. THE MED-GOLD COMMUNITY

The steps taken for starting to build up the MED-GOLD community focus on the relevance of the stakeholders for the activities planned during MED-GOLD. This relevance is further explained in the next three paragraphs.

For the initial development of the community, there were taken into consideration organisations connected with MED-GOLD industrial partners, in Spain (DCOOP), Portugal (SOGRAPE), and Italy (Barilla). An additional number of organisations operating at European level were identified through screening of grey literature (RD. 1, RD.2, RD. 3, RD. 4, and RD. 5). Furthermore, a number of relevant European projects and initiatives were identified from CORDIS database, which will be approached for clustering purposes, as detailed in section 3.1.

The MED-GOLD community is being build up through a range of actions. More specifically, the starting point was the information collected on European and national organisations relevant for Task 1.1. “Regulatory and institutional mapping and market analysis” of MED-GOLD. These organisations will be approached and informed of MED-GOLD and be given the option to join the MED-GOLD mailing list in the first stage.

In addition, direct contact with key European organisations (e.g. networks, associations, private companies including SMEs) operating in the MED-GOLD targeted sectors is currently being pursued. These organisations will act as multiplier organisations and as an entry point to other climate service end-users operating in the three targeted sectors.

A mailing list of the MED-GOLD community is being compiled and will be used for future dissemination and engagement activities, such as, registering for the online user forum (Task 5.2.), online survey (Task 5.2.) and periodic bulletins and webinars (Task 5.3). The contact information of MED-GOLD community is stored in an Excel database which is accessible to the MED-GOLD team.

Currently, the MED-GOLD community includes public and private organisations operating in the sectors of interest - olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat - to the potential end-users of the pilot climate services being developed within MED-GOLD. This community is expected to act as a ‘bed test’ to discuss, explore and validate the developments and findings from the pilot climate services in work packages 2, 3 and 4. The involvement in this community will allow the participants to be continuously informed of the latest advances of the research as well as to contribute to the validation and upscaling activities that will be pursued in Task 5.2. “Engaging, validating and exploiting the pilot services with the MED-GOLD community”.

At the time of this report (25th May 2018), approximately 280 organisations have been identified and inserted into work package 5 database of contacts. These include organisations operating at the European, national and local levels and cover relevant stakeholders in the olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta sectors (section 3.1.), in the agriculture sector (section 3.2.), and in the climate services sector (section 3.3.). The categories of stakeholders for each of these sectors is described in the following sections.

3.1. STAKEHOLDERS OPERATING IN THE OLIVES/OLIVE OIL, GRAPES/ WINE AND DURUM WHEAT/PASTA SECTORS

For these sectors, stakeholders were identified within and outside the supply/value chains, as detailed in Table 3-1.

The organisations outside Europe will be approached in line with Task 6.3: “Dissemination and capacity building towards policy-makers and general public” of MED-GOLD. This task supports the implementation of the EU current mitigation and adaptation policies to climate change through a better-informed decision making and through its adoption in key vulnerable sectors, as those under the umbrella of bio-economy. This involves awareness actions regarding the future co-developed climate services on a more general public, including other sectors outside the MED-GOLD community.

Additionally, there were identified EU projects and initiatives, which will be approached for clustering purposes, in line with Task 6.1. “Interactions with other initiatives” of MED-GOLD. This task will pursue dissemination synergies with other EU initiatives. Such interactions will also allow to foster effective international cooperation.

Table 3-1 Stakeholders operating in olive/olive oil, grape/wine, durum wheat/pasta sectors

Stakeholders		Olives/olive oil		Grapes/wine		Durum wheat/pasta	
Producers	Description	Those using climate data and services for application of agro-chemicals (fertilizers, pesticides) and harvest timing, selection of olive tree/grape/durum wheat varieties, decisions related to storage and purchase of weather insurance					
	Country/Total number per country	Cyprus Turkey Spain	1 1 3	Spain Portugal France Germany Cyprus Italy UK Malta	3 3 2 1 1 2 1 1	Italy Romania Spain	1 2 1
Processors	Description	Those using climate data and services to identify peak seasons, depending on the expected harvest time, and to scout locations for new plant sites					
	Country/Total number per country	Egypt Malta Italy Spain Portugal	1 1 6 3 1	Spain Portugal France Germany Cyprus Italy UK Malta	3 3 2 1 1 2 1 1	Italy France Spain Sweden Turkey Brazil South Africa Germany Luxembourg	64 12 2 1 1 1 1 1 1
Purveyors	Description	Include regulating bodies, advisory and business-science networks and organisations. They have a role in deciding on, and informing, climate related adaptation actions of their members and clients and the potential to link their members and clients with climate service suppliers					
	Country/Total number per country	France Italy USA Spain Tunisia Morocco Turkey USA	1 2 2 5 1 1 11 2	Belgium France Germany Greece Italy Netherlands Portugal Romania Slovenia Spain Switzerland	2 2 2 1 1 1 4 1 1 4 1	Belgium Italy UK France	1 3 2 3
Researchers	Description	Those using climate data in relation to climate change and variability impacts on olives/grapes/durum wheat production					
	Country/Total number per country	Spain USA Italy Turkey	3 1 1 2	Spain France USA Portugal	1 1 2 1	Italy	2
EU projects	Description	Those who will be approached for clustering purposes as detailed in section 3.1.					
	Country/Total number per country	EU	2	EU	1	-	-
Overall total	-	-	51*	-	54*	-	99*

*These numbers are valid at the date of this report (25th May 2018) and will change during MED-GOLD timeline

3.2. STAKEHOLDERS OPERATING IN THE WIDER AGRICULTURE SECTOR

For the agriculture sector in general, stakeholders were identified within and outside the supply/value chain, as detailed in Table 3-2.

These organisations will be approached in line with Task 6.3., as detailed in section 3.1. “Contacts from the agricultural sectors regarding other crops” (i.e. Colombian coffee), as well as forestry, livestock and fisheries sectors will be particularly targeted. The crops produced by these organisations include: vegetables (celery, tomato, sweet peppers, asparagus, cucurbitaceous, eggplant, cauliflower, and artichokes), fruits (melon, peaches, olives, grapes, and almonds), cereals (durum wheat, rice, millet, and oat), cocoa, sugar beet, sugar cane, cotton, potatoes, pulses, and flowers. Some of them raise livestock (sheep, beef and dairy livestock, goats) and fish.

Additionally, we also identified EU and international projects and initiatives, which will be approached for clustering purposes, in line with Task 6.1. of MED-GOLD, as detailed in section 3.1.

Table 3-2 Stakeholders operating in the wider agriculture sector

Stakeholders		Agriculture	
Producers	Description	Those using climate data and services for application of agro-chemicals (fertilizers, pesticides) and harvest timing, selection of crop type and crop varieties, decisions related to crop storage and purchase of weather insurance	
	Country/Crop or sector/Total number per country	Italy/fishery	1
		Italy/crops and livestock	8
		Spain/cereal, fruits and vegetables	3
		France/cereal, fruits, and vegetables	3
Processors	Description	Those using climate data and services to identify peak seasons, depending on the expected crop harvest time, and scout locations for new plant sites	
	Country/Crop or sector/Total number per country	Italy/cereals, fruits and vegetables	3
		France/crops and livestock	3
Input manufacturers	Description	Those using climate forecasts to develop new crop varieties and to schedule production of fungicides and pesticides	
	Country/Crop or sector/Total number per country	Italy/cereals, fruits, vegetables, flowers	1
Extensionists	Description	Those promoting good agricultural practices related to the use of climate services for informed decisions related to crop production	
	Country/Crop or sector/Total number per country	Croatia/rural development	1
		France/rural development	1
		Italy/crops and fishery	1
	Description	Include opinion leaders, regulating bodies, intergovernmental, governmental and policy support organisations, advisory, and agricultural services businesses. They have a role in deciding on, and informing, climate related adaptation actions of their members and clients and the potential to link their members and clients with climate service suppliers	

Stakeholders		Agriculture	
Purveyors	Country/Sector/Total number per country	Italy/agricultural services provider	1
		Italy/regulating body	1
		Italy/policy supporter	1
		Italy/consultant	2
		Spain/regulating body	1
		Spain/advisory organisation	1
		Belgium/opinion leader	1
		Portugal/regulating body	1
		France/intergovernmental organisation	1
		France/governmental organisations	2
		France/regulating body	1
		France/consultant	1
		Turkey/regulating body	2
		Turkey/governmental organisation	1
Researchers	Description	Those using climate data in relation to climate change and variability impacts on crop production	
	Country/Total number per country	Spain	4
		France	3
Italy		1	
Greece		2	
EU/ international projects	Description	Those who will be approached for clustering purposes as detailed in section 3.1.	
	Country/Total number per country	EU	5
EU - China		1	
Overall total	-	-	58*

*These numbers are valid at the date of this report (25th May 2018) and will change during MED-GOLD timeline

3.3. STAKEHOLDERS OPERATING IN CLIMATE SERVICES

Besides the sectors mentioned above, other stakeholders were identified along the different stages of climate services supply chain, as illustrated in Table 3-3.

The organisations outside Europe will be approached in line with Task 6.3, as detailed in section 3.1.

Additionally, there were identified EU and international projects and initiatives, which will be approached for clustering purposes, in line with Task 6.1., as detailed in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3 Stakeholders operating in climate services

Stakeholders		Climate services	
Policy makers	Description	Those who will be approached from the perspective of informing policy making processes so as to support the implementation of the EU current mitigation and adaptation policies to climate change in key vulnerable sectors, such as the agricultural ones	
	Country/Total number per country	Denmark USA Belgium	1 1 1
Purveyors	Description	Include policy support organisations, advisory and consultancy organisations and networks. They have a role in informing climate related adaptation actions of their clients and the potential to link climate service suppliers and end-users	
	Country/Total number per country	UK Belgium Hungary France Switzerland Italy Costa Rica	2 1 1 1 1 1
EU/ international projects	Description	Those who will be approached in line with Task 6.1.” Interactions with other initiatives” of MED-GOLD. This action will pursue clustering with other climate service related European Commission funded projects via H2020 or other complementary programmes. Such interactions will allow to foster effective international cooperation as well; for instance, coordination with existing H2020 projects on the same topic (i.e. EU-MACS, MARCO) will ensure that any potential overlapping is avoided	
	Country/Total number per country	EU EU-Kenya-Hong Kong	10 1
Overall total	-	-	21*

*These numbers are valid at the date of this report (25th May 2018) and will change during MED-GOLD timeline

4. NEXT STEPS

4.1. IMMEDIATE ACTIONS TO ENGAGE WITH THE MED-GOLD COMMUNITY

The first step to engage with the MED-GOLD community will be to send introductory emails to the organisations in the current database of contacts. The emails will explain MED-GOLD, the purpose of the MED-GOLD community and will provide the opportunity for these organisations to register in the community and its various engagement activities that are planned throughout MED-GOLD. A one page informative paper on MED-GOLD (Annex A) will also be attached to these emails.

The organisations interested in joining the MED-GOLD community have the option to subscribe to the sector of interest via MED-GOLD website (<https://www.med-gold.eu/>). Additionally, where necessary, there will be introductory phone calls and follow up calls to help recruit these organisations into the MED-GOLD community.

The stakeholders joining the MED-GOLD community will be offered the possibility of selecting their interest to take part in a range of activities including:

- Attending online webinars to learn about specific themes of interest to the MED-GOLD sectors;
- Receiving periodic bulletins, newsletters, and other communication and dissemination materials on the latest developments in the climate services being developed in MED-GOLD, their value and benefits to organisations, as well as the use of climate services to support decision-making;
- Participating on an online forum that allows them to discuss and ask questions about the climate services developed to the MED-GOLD team;
- Participating on an online survey, to help MED-GOLD team understand the potential use and replicability of the climate services developed in organisations similar to the contacted ones;
- Attending participatory workshops, to learn more about the climate services developed, discuss and assess the potential for upscaling and applying the climate services developed in MED-GOLD in other organisations operating in these sectors.

In order to ensure successful engagement with the MED-GOLD community, some of the activities listed above can be carried out in local languages. More specifically, the initial scoping workshop with relevant stakeholders in the sector of olives/olive oil will be held in Spanish, to ensure successful assessment of the key vulnerabilities, information needs, and critical decisions within this sector, in line with Task 2.1. "Appraising needs and critical decisions". Similarly, the interviews with SOGRAPE key personnel were held in Portuguese, for assessing the key vulnerabilities, information needs, and critical decisions within grapes/wine sector, in line with Task 3.1. "Appraising needs and critical decisions". Also, the initial scoping workshop with relevant stakeholders in the sector of durum wheat/pasta was held in Italian, to ensure successful assessment of the key vulnerabilities, information needs, and critical decisions within this sector, in line with Task 4.1. "Appraising needs and critical decisions".

Other engaging activities which can take place in local languages depend on the target audience and may include press releases to national/regional media and webinars.

4.2. CONTINUOUS DEVELOPMENT OF THE MED-GOLD COMMUNITY

To continue developing the community, the following activities will be pursued:

1. Identify and contact missing/under-represented relevant categories of climate services' end-users within and outside the supply/value chains for olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, durum wheat/pasta, and agriculture sectors, as illustrated in Table 3-4.

Table 3-4 Missing/under-represented categories of stakeholders per sector

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Category of stakeholder	Olives/olive oil sector		Grapes/wine sector		Durum wheat/pasta sector		Agriculture sector	
	WITHIN supply/value chain	OUTSIDE supply/value chain						
Input (seeds, agro-chemicals) manufacturers	x		x		x		x	
Producers					x			
Processors							x	
Extensionists		x		x		x		x
Researchers		x		x		x		
Policy makers		x		x		x		x
Weather insurance companies*		x		x		x		x
Agricultural banks*		x		x		x		x
Investors*		x		x		x		x
EU/international projects for clustering		x		x		x		

*These categories of stakeholders are currently missing from MED-GOLD database of contacts and will be identified as the MED-GOLD community develops

2. At sector level, there will be filled in the gaps for the under-represented sectors:

- a. Olives/olive oil
- b. Grapes/wine
- c. Agriculture

It worth mentioning here that the gaps mentioned at point 2 were identified based on the overall number of stakeholders per sector, indicating durum wheat sector as being the largest represented (97 stakeholders) compared with olives/olive oil (51 stakeholders), grapes/wine (54 stakeholders), and agriculture (58 stakeholders), as illustrated in Table 3-1.

However, in terms of range of stakeholders, the durum wheat sector was the poorest represented at the time of this report (25th May 2018), with a large number of processors prevailing the other categories of stakeholders. This gap will be filled as the MED-GOLD community develops.

3. Identify and contact stakeholders in all the countries relevant for olives, grapes and durum wheat production, in particular, and other agricultural sectors of interest (coffee, fisheries, forestry, livestock), in general, in EU and worldwide. To be more specific, for olives/olive oil sector, for example, the starting point is represented by the relevant countries identified for the purposes of Task 1.1. "Regulatory and institutional mapping and market analysis": Spain, Italy, Greece, Portugal, France, Cyprus, Slovenia, Malta, Croatia, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, and Turkey.

4.3. MED-GOLD COMMUNITY TO DATE

Since the submission of this report, we have been actively reaching out to other organisations in Europe in order to address some of the gaps identified in table 3-4. and increase the representation of relevant stakeholders in the MED-GOLD community.

The table below illustrates the progress made since deliverable D 5.1. was submitted, in terms of numbers of organisations interested in MED-GOLD project, per sector and country,

Table 3-5 Registered MED-GOLD Community members, per sector and country

Country	Sector				
	Olive-olive oil	Grape-wine	Durum wheat-pasta	Agriculture	Climate
Portugal	4	28	-	4	2
Italy	3	8	14	17	-
Greece	2	-	-	11	-
Spain	2	6	1	1	-
Brasil	1	1	-	-	-
France	-	1	-	-	1
Bulgaria	-	1	1	1	-
Slovenia	-	1	-	-	-
Romania	-	-	-	2	-
Denmark	-	-	-	1	-
Morocco	-	-	-	1	-
Luxembourg	-	-	-	1	-
United Kingdom	-	-	-	-	1
TOTAL	12	46	16	39	4

***information valid on 29th March 2019, which will change as the Community develops**

5. CONCLUSIONS

Relevant organisations have been identified to join the MED-GOLD community. These organisations will be approached via introductory emails or calls, as necessary, informed on MED-GOLD and MED-GOLD community, and be given the opportunity to register in the community and its various engagement activities that are planned throughout MED-GOLD.

To continue developing the MED-GOLD community, there will be pursued activities relating to: identification and approaching of missing/under-represented relevant categories of climate services' end-users for olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, durum wheat/pasta, and agriculture sectors; filling in the gaps for the under-represented sectors; identification and approaching stakeholders in all the countries relevant for olive, grape and durum wheat production, in particular, and other agricultural sectors of interest (coffee, fisheries, forestry, livestock), in general, in EU and worldwide

ANNEX A. MED-GOLD PROJECT INFORMATIVE SHEET

MED-GOLD

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776467

MED-GOLD (Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems) is a four-year research and innovation project funded by Horizon 2020, the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. MED-GOLD is led by the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA) and involves 15 other partners, including industrial partners, meteorological institutes, universities and research centres, computing centres and service provider companies from Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, United Kingdom and Colombia (for more information, see: <https://www.MED-GOLD.eu>).

The **aim of MED-GOLD** is to develop climate services specific to agriculture, a sector directly impacted by climate variability and change, so as to minimize climate-driven risks and seize opportunities for three traditional products of the Mediterranean food system: **Olive Oil, Wine, and Pasta**.

Climate services, broadly understood as the transformation of climate data and other information into customised products (e.g. climate change projections, climatic trends, advice on best practices), have the potential to better inform and improve decision-making and, therefore, increase competitiveness and resilience of the agricultural sector to climate variability and change in the short and long term.

The **MED-GOLD Community** is a fundamental part of MED-GOLD. The community will be composed of public and private policy and decision-makers operating in the sectors of interest to MED-GOLD: olives/olive oil, grapes/wine and durum wheat/pasta. This community will be involved and engaged with the ongoing research developments achieved within MED-GOLD and will help explore and validate the usefulness and usability of the climate services developed for each of the sectors in MED-GOLD.

Why should you be interested in joining the MED-GOLD Community?

MED-GOLD will develop climate services for three sectors – olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta – to demonstrate the applicability, usefulness, added value, and benefits of such services within key decision-making processes. This will involve development of prototype tools for delivering the services, and an assessment of business opportunities for the three sectors.

Your participation in the MED-GOLD Community is essential to help us to understand and identify your needs in terms of climate services and climate impact information. *Once identified, your needs will be translated into tailored climate services aimed at the exploitation of new opportunities for your activity while contributing to the minimization of climate-driven risks and the reduction of the associated costs.* For successful development of these services, you will be timely informed of, and asked for feedback on, the project developments.

What would you be invited to do as part of the MED-GOLD Community?

- Invitation to attend **webinars** to learn about specific topics related to the MED-GOLD sectors;
- Receive **periodic bulletins** on the latest developments in the climate services being developed in MED-GOLD, their value and benefits to organisations as well as the use of climate services to support decision-making;
- Participation in an **online forum** that provides you a direct communication with the MED-GOLD team to discuss and ask questions about the climate services developed;
- Participation in an **online survey**, to help us understand the potential use and replicability of the climate services developed in organisations like yours;

- Invitation to attend **participatory workshops**, to learn more about the climate services developed, discuss and assess the potential for upscaling and applying them in other organisations operating in the MED-GOLD sectors.

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